

iJERResearch

International Journal of Education and Research
Vol-1, Number 3, December - 2024 | Peer-Reviewed
Journal ISSN 2764-9733 | ijerresearch.org
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14341325

THE IMPORTANCE OF DISTANCE EDUCATION FOR THE DEMOCRATIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION

AUTHOR

Karen Santos D'Oliveira: Post-doctoral trainee in Educational Sciences at Universidad UNIDA - PY, Educational Counselor and Primary School Teacher at Maricá City Hall/R.J.
Contact: oliveira.karen@yahoo.com.br / 21 - 99 598.3157

ABSTRACT

Distance education (DE) is an essential tool for democratizing access to higher education. This study investigates the influence of distance education in this context, exploring its benefits and challenges. The analysis of the results highlights the growing acceptance of this modality and its impact on the inclusion of diverse audiences. We conclude that DE plays a vital role in promoting the democratization of higher education, providing flexibility and accessibility.

KEYWORDS: Distance education. Higher education. Democratization.